

MASTER's second Open Call projects complete their execution phase, delivering new XR and robotics training solutions

The 24 projects selected under the EU-funded research project MASTER's second Open Call have completed their execution phase. This marks an important milestone in the expansion of the MASTER ecosystem for XR-based robotics training.

The second Open Call was launched to support the validation of extended reality (XR) technologies in learning environments. Innovators, researchers, educators and technology developers from the selected projects received financial support and technical guidance to develop, test and demonstrate novel XR applications addressing industrial training challenges.

The projects explored a range of use cases combining XR, artificial intelligence and robotics to create immersive, accessible and effective learning experiences. Their solutions address key industrial training needs, including human-robot collaboration, robot programming, maintenance and troubleshooting, safety and ergonomics, manufacturing processes, digital twins, machine tending, welding inspection and agricultural robotics.

Solutions

Several projects focused on making robotics education more accessible to non-expert users through intuitive XR interfaces and gamified learning experiences. Others leveraged AI to automate content generation, personalise training, or create intelligent virtual instructors capable of interacting naturally with learners. Many solutions also used digital twins and realistic industrial simulations, to allow trainees to gain practical experience in safe and controlled virtual environments.

Among the developed solutions are immersive training platforms for collaborative robot programming, virtual learning factories, AI-powered robotics simulators, maintenance training environments, ergonomics-focused learning experiences and advanced XR tools for understanding robotics concepts and industrial processes. These projects demonstrate the potential of XR technologies to support workforce upskilling and lifelong learning in increasingly automated industrial environments.

Building on the foundations established by MASTER's first Open Call, the second cohort further strengthens the project's vision of creating an open ecosystem for XR-enabled robotics training. The solutions developed contribute new training methodologies, learning scenarios and technological approaches that can support education providers, training centres and industrial organisations in preparing workers for the factories of the future.

The successful completion of the execution phase represents not only the culmination of the projects' development activities, but also the beginning of their potential impact beyond the MASTER project.

Innovation ecosystem

"One of MASTER's main ambitions has always been to create an ecosystem where innovation can flourish beyond the core consortium," said Panagiotis Karagiannis of the LMS, University of Patras and the project coordinator of MASTER. **"The results delivered by the 24 projects supported through the 2nd Open Call demonstrate the creativity and expertise of Europe's XR and robotics communities. Their solutions expand the MASTER ecosystem with new training approaches, technologies and use cases that will continue generating impact long after the project ends."**

The results show how immersive technologies can bridge skills gaps, improve training effectiveness and support the adoption of robotics and automation across multiple industrial sectors. As MASTER approaches its end, the achievements of the second Open Call winners highlight the creativity, expertise and innovation present within Europe's XR and robotics communities while providing valuable insights into the future of immersive industrial training.

The 24 projects supported under the second Open Call are: AIR-XR, AIXRIG, AI-XRobo, ARCHIVE, CoBotXpeRience, EMPAIRED, Ergon-PICK, FARMTRON-XR, HRC-XR Trainer, ICETeachXR, REACH-NEXT, RoboXR, RobWIQ-XRT, SkillXR, SMART-XR, TI-RAX, TRiFlex-C, TRUST, VIRAMM, X-HRC, XR-GRIT, X-MAIN, XRplained and XR-SHIELDS.

The completion of the execution phase marks an important step in the transfer of XR and AI innovations from research into practical educational and industrial applications, contributing to a more skilled, adaptable and future-ready European workforce.

About MASTER

As industries transition to Industry 4.0 production models, robots are becoming more prevalent in industrial processes. XR technologies are also entering this domain, with successful cases in training, remote assistance, and contextual information access.

MASTER enhances robotics training in manufacturing with its XR platform. It integrates key functionalities, creating safe and flexible robotic environments with advanced interaction mechanisms. The project delivers rich training content and invites third-party contributions through two Open Calls.

<https://www.master-xr.eu/>